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Bernhard Braunecker

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Optical Wavefront Sensing

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Introduction

We described in No. 71 of this journal the measurement of the internal centering state of e.g. lithographic lenses, a rather special task in optical factories. In the following we focus more on questions of daily industrial business how to control the wavefront (WF) shape of optical beams. This could concern laser power systems for micro-machining applications, where the beam profile of the laser has to be modified appropriately either to drill holes or to polish surfaces or to anneal the material to relax internal tensions. Or WF measurements in astronomy when the image of a star is blurred by the turbulence of the earth atmosphere. To get rid of this distortion modern telescopes include a so called adaptive optical mirror which reflection surface can be mechanically shaped to compensate the distortion of the star WF. This is controlled by a WF sensor and allows to retrieve full image resolution. We will describe WF-sensors which are either commercially available or still in development or even just an idea. Each method has its pros/cons, and the user has to find his optimal solution.

We will start with the simplest approach, the Hartmann sensor, and extend its concept to more efficient, smaller and faster versions.

WF measuring Concept

Most WF sensors work with a 2f-optics (Fig. 1), where the light wave in the lens entrance pupil (EP) located at $z = -f$ is transferred to its Fouriertransform in the image plane (IM) at $z = +f$, where f is the lens focal length. The lens characterized by its F-Number $\equiv f/D_{EP}$, where D_{EP} is the EP diameter, should be designed that a plane wave with a preset tilt angle α still leads to a diffraction limited spot at position $r = f \cdot \tan(\alpha)$ in IM. To measure the full profile of an incident WF, one divides first the EP in many small sub-apertures and second inserts a position sensitive detector PSD in the image plane IM.

The PSD measures both, the spot intensity I and the centroid vector of the light distribution $\mathbf{R}(x,y)$. It will be shown next that \mathbf{R} is directly proportional to the WF-gradient in EP, which is the average slope of the WF across all open

sub-apertures. As a first approach, the classical method, one moves a single hole across the beam cross section D_{EP} , which delivers enough information to retrieve the complete WF from all averaged local WF slopes. But there are more efficient strategies which we will explain next.

Theory

The WF in the entrance plane is described by the complex amplitude $\hat{U}(\mathbf{v}) = A(\mathbf{v}) \exp(i\psi(\mathbf{v}))$, where the WF error ψ is the deviation from a perfect plane wave expressed as phase term¹. If the lens works diffraction-limited, as we assumed, the complex amplitude $U(\mathbf{r})$ in IM is up to irrelevant phase factors equal to the Fourier transform $U(\mathbf{r}) = \int d\mathbf{v} \hat{U}(\mathbf{v}) \exp(-i\mathbf{r}\mathbf{v})$. The measured quantities at the PSD are the intensity

$$I = \int d\mathbf{r} |U(\mathbf{r})|^2 \quad (1a)$$

and the intensity centroid

$$\mathbf{R} = \int d\mathbf{r} \mathbf{r} |U(\mathbf{r})|^2 \quad (1b).$$

The sampling of the WF in the EP is performed by a code mask F of one or many small holes, called sub-apertures. Then $F(\mathbf{v})$ is multiplied with $\hat{U}(\mathbf{v})$. Inserting the Fourier transform in (1a) and (1b) leads to

$$I = \int d\mathbf{v} [F(\mathbf{v}) A(\mathbf{v})]^2 \quad (2a)$$

and

$$\mathbf{R} = \int d\mathbf{v} \text{Im}\{F(\mathbf{v}) A(\mathbf{v}) \cdot \nabla[F(\mathbf{v}) A(\mathbf{v})] + i(F(\mathbf{v}) A(\mathbf{v}))^2 \cdot \nabla[\psi(\mathbf{v})]\} \quad (2b)$$

where we applied the Fourier theorem of differentiating and the integration by parts. It will be shown that measuring I_m and \mathbf{R}_m for a complete set of filters F_m ($m = 1 \dots M$) allows to determine $A(\mathbf{v})$ and the WF-gradient function $\nabla[\psi(\mathbf{v})]$. The latter can be integrated across the whole aperture to obtain $\psi(\mathbf{v})$ up to an additive constant. In most cases the phase function ψ can be developed to $K = 24$ or 36 Zernike polynomials $Z_k(\mathbf{v})$, $k = 1 \dots K$, leading to $\psi(\mathbf{v}) = \sum c_k Z_k(\mathbf{v})$. The measurement goal is to determine the Zernike coefficients c_k .

If the full aperture is scanned at N sampling positions \mathbf{v}_n by M measurements of I_m and \mathbf{R}_m , the unknown amplitude values A_n and the Zernike coefficients c_k are obtained by solving the set of M linear equations (3a) and (3b), written in matrix notation

$$F_{M,N}^2 \cdot A_{N,1}^2 = I_{M,1} \quad (3a)$$

leading to

$$A_{N,1}^2 = (F_{N,M}^T \cdot F_{M,N})^{-1} \cdot F_{N,M}^T \cdot I_{M,1}$$

and to

$$F_{M,N}^2 \cdot \text{diag}(A^2)_{N,N} \cdot \nabla Z_{N,K} \cdot c_{K,1} \equiv L_{M,K} \cdot c_{K,1} = \mathbf{R}_{M,1} \quad (3b)$$

¹ It is usual to express the EP-coordinates r_p by the spatial frequencies $\mathbf{v} = k/f \mathbf{r}_p$ using $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, λ the wavelength and f the focal length.

Fig. 1: Hartmann sensor using a 2f System. The WF in the entrance pupil EP is Fouriertransformed in the image plane. The EP is covered by a rotating code mask. The position sensitive detector PSD measures the intensity centroid.

resulting in

$$c_{K,1} = (L_{K,M}^T \cdot L_{M,K})^{-1} \cdot L_{K,M}^T \cdot R_{M,1} \quad (3c)$$

where we ignored here the first term with $\nabla[F(\mathbf{v}) A(\mathbf{v})]$ in (2b, 3b) as of minor importance.

Single Hole Hartmann WFS

The most simply WF sensor is the historical Hartmann sensor where the beam cross section, illustrated by the red circle in Fig. 2, is scanned in polar coordinates by a rotating Nipkow-disk² with several holes. In our example seven holes are arranged in such a way, that when one hole enters the red circle, its adjacent radial neighbor just leaves it. This assures that at any time only one hole is inside the circle, and the measured WF is directly the corresponding local one, so $M = N$ in (3a, 3b) and function $F_n = \text{circ}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}_n, r_{\text{Hole}})$.

Fig. 2: Example of a Hartmann disk with seven scanning holes. The red circle is the beam cross section in the EP. The hole arrangement in magenta shows start of scan, in yellow at scanning half time and in blue at end of scan. At any time there is only one hole inside the red EP area.

Hadamard coded Hartmann WFS

The main disadvantage of the Hartmann single hole method is its inefficiency. The low intensity transmitted through the small hole requires long integration times to achieve an acceptable signal to noise ratio (SNR)³. The solution is to encode the WF by a set of code masks that about 50 % of the incident intensity is permanently measured (Fig. 3). The price to pay, however, is the numerical decoding after the measurements.

The code should be a) binary (hole or no hole), b) cyclic, meaning when the code pattern is rotated by one code element, a new pattern appears, c) orthogonal d) should have a fast decoding algorithm similar to the Fast Fourier transform FFT and e) the code length should be a product of two nearly equal numbers m_a and m_b to fold the pattern in two dimensions to cover the beam cross section.

Fig. 3: Hartmann disk with M-sequence code of $N = 63$ elements. The red segment is the area where the WF is measured. The same color e.g. magenta, shows how the code elements 1 ... 63 are arranged in 7 segments (separated by green lines) of 9 elements each. When rotating the disk by one hole step, a new orthogonal 2D-code pattern covers the WF in the red segment.

A good choice as code mask is the S-matrix, derived from so called M-sequences⁴. The decoding algorithm is based on the Fast Hadamard Transform FHT, faster than the FFT since binary, which, however, needs two permutations of the input and output vector. But there are clever possibilities to make both permutations equal to reduce the computation effort. We applied in many industrial applications M-sequences of length $N = 2^m - 1$ with m even as $N = 63 = 7 \times 9$, or $255 = 15 \times 17$, or $1023 = 31 \times 33$, but also $N = 65535 = 255 \times 257$ and larger would be possible. This, however, would need a lot of computing power and be more the case for big astronomical applications.

Then (3b) is rewritten as

$$S_{N,N} \cdot \text{diag}(A^2)_{N,N} \cdot \nabla Z_{N,K} \cdot c_{K,1} \equiv S_{N,N} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{N,1} = \mathbf{R}_{N,1} \quad (4)$$

where $S_{N,N}$ is the S-matrix and solve for

$$\mathbf{x}_{N,1} = (S_{N,N})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{N,1} \quad (5)$$

to obtain

$$c_{K,1} = (\nabla Z_{K,N}^T \cdot \nabla Z_{N,K})^{-1} \cdot \nabla Z_{K,N}^T \cdot \text{diag}(A^2)_{N,N} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{N,1} \quad (6)$$

by using the known values of $A_{N,N}$ and the Zernike gradient functions $\nabla Z_{K,N}(\mathbf{r})$.

When we developed some years ago such an encoded WF sensor for ESA, we chose a code of $N = 63$ elements folded

² The Nipkow disk was used as first scanner for TV images in the 1920 years.

³ The spatial encoding of an aperture (red circle in Fig. 2) with masks of about 50% transmittance is necessary if the aperture is the human thyroid gland enriched with the isotope iodine-131. Then all emitted gamma quanta (364 keV) should be permanently measured to keep the injected dose small.

⁴ E E Fenimore 'Large symmetric Pi transformations for Hadamard transforms', Applied Optics, Vol. 22, No. 6, 15 March 1983

in circular segments of 7×9 elements (Fig. 3), together with a PSD characterized by a noise equivalent displacement $\text{NeD} = 25 \text{ nm/Hz}^{-1/2}$ which value was experimentally verified at an incident power of $1 \mu\text{W}$. Since we measured each code pattern 80 ms, the NeD was $25 \text{ nm} / \text{Hz}^{-1/2} / \sqrt{80 \text{ ms}} = 88 \text{ nm}$. Using a Fourier optics of $F\# = 6.25$ and $\lambda = 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ led to a noise equivalent WF error $\partial x = \text{NeD}/(2 F\#) = 0.0064 \mu\text{m}$, i.e. $\lambda/100$ rms.

The WF resolution was verified with a test laser beam of 0.611λ pV (0.104λ rms) WF error. The total measurement time was however $63 \times 80 \text{ ms} = 5 \text{ s}$.

Both Hartmann versions based on rotating disks are very accurate, but large scaled and slow in operation. This is not a problem when testing the image quality of optical systems in the lab or in the factory. In those cases, however, where WF measurements in real time are required, one needs other configurations of the Hartmann method.

Shack-Hartmann WFS

This is the most used technical version today. The incident WF of diameter D_{Beam} is imaged by an array of lenslets (diameter d_{Lenslet}) on a 2D-CMOS sensor of diameter $D_{\text{CMOS}} = D_{\text{Beam}}$ and pixel diameter d_{Pixel} . Therefore each lenslet addresses $m = d_{\text{Lenslet}} / d_{\text{Pixel}}$ pixels which determines the measurement range.

Example: For $D_{\text{Beam}} = 25 \text{ mm}$ and $d_{\text{Lenslet}} = 0.1 \text{ mm}$ we have 250 lenslets in one direction. If the focal length f is 25 mm, then the maximum WF angular range is $\pm 2 \text{ mrad}$. Measuring with a wavelength $\lambda = 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ yields a maximum WF tilt range of $\pm 5 \lambda$. If the CMOS pixel size is $10 \mu\text{m}$, the WF resolution is about $\lambda/25$ rms, which is sufficient for most industrial tasks.

Hartmann WFS with Digital Light Projector®

If one needs the high WF resolution of the Hadamard-Hartmann sensor but with shorter measurement times, then the

Fig. 4: The incident WF (blue line) is imaged as a dented spot array on the CMOS sensor. This allows to calculate the WF tilt angle across each lenslet aperture and to reconstruct the total WF error.

following idea might be interesting. It still keeps the modern 2-step concept (physical encoding by masks plus numerical decoding), but substitutes the mechanical disk by MEMS technology which significantly increases the speed and reduces the size. The code disk is replaced by a digital light projector (DLP) which is used more and more in TV and display applications⁵. It consists of a 2D-MEMS array of switchable mirror pixels of about $10 \mu\text{m}$ width and pitch that can be electrically deflected about 20° with video or even higher frame frequencies.

Fig. 5: Concept of a DLP - WFS. The incident WF is reflected from the DLP switching elements (left) and focused by the mirror optics (right) on the PSD (top).

The light from a not-deflected DLP element corresponds to a code bit 'one' and is recorded by the PSD, otherwise stopped at the PSD-aperture as code bit 'zero'. In the lower part the perfect WF of a laser diode is used for autocalibration on demand.

In Fig. 5 we sketch the idea of such a compact Hadamard WF sensor with a beamsplitter cube as the central optical element. The incoming WF is reflected from the DLP and Fourier-transformed by a parabolic mirror on the PSD. The PSD is covered with a field stop with an aperture wide enough to accept the diffraction pattern arising from a not-deflected mirror element of some degrees plus some margin for the expected WF tilt angle range. A not-deflected mirror pixel corresponds to a '1' in our coding mask scheme and is registered by the PSD, while a code element '0' is implemented as a mirror pixel deflecting of 20° and thus not registered. To minimize the intensity loss, the beamsplitting layer is polarization sensitive, i.e. highly reflecting s-polarized light, but fully transmitting p-polarized light. The necessary change of polarization is accomplished by a linear polarizer at the entrance side and two $\lambda/4$ waveplates (orange and yellow plates in Fig. 5).

The idea to use a DLP for multiplex signal coding of light is getting more and more attractive for imaging tasks in microscopes and cameras, using only one pixel sensor according

⁵ <https://www.ti.com/de-de/dlp-chip/products.html>

to equation (1a)⁶. But the version here with a PSD is much more powerful since it measures intensity and phase. We presented the idea in 2010 using a DLP D4X00Kit of Texas Instruments (1920 x 1080) pixels of 10 μm pitch⁷, but unfortunately could never experimentally realize it. Especially the trade-off between the DLP's fast switching speed and the frequency dependent NeD of the PSD needs to be better understood, but also how exactly returns each mirror element after deflection back to a reflection angle zero? This potential error source, however, could be eliminated by adding an on-line calibration module, as shown in the lower part of Fig. 5. A laser diode with slightly different wavelength produces a perfect plane wave and thus can measure the true zero-deflection angle of each pixel element whenever needed. To minimize the intensity loss in the operating mode the beamsplitter coating of the calibration cube is dichroic⁸.

Space Communications

Such a fast, accurate and robust WFS is best suited for real-time space applications. In the future the data transfer between satellites is performed by laser light, which includes the up- and down link from satellite to ground stations (Fig. 6). The laser WF is, however, blurred by turbulences in the atmosphere which led to an intensity loss at the receiver telescopes. To keep a certain SNR necessary for a preset bit error rate would need longer integration times resulting in smaller data rates. But installing an adaptive optical element

⁶ Laser Focus World, No. 48 (July 2010), p 48. www.laserfocusworld.com

⁷ Darmstädter Kolloquium für optische Messtechnik (Dakom), 11.03.2010

⁸ Even there is no need to use a (cyclic) M-sequence as code pattern as in the case of the rotating disk, the advantage is the nearly same signal intensity of all M-transforms. This is different to Fourier or Hadamard transformations with their large DC peak, and results in a better use of the dynamic range of the PSD sensor.

Fig. 6: Ground station on Tenerife for up- and down link to satellites using laser light as data carrier. Image: GA-Synopta GmbH.

in one or both telescopes controlled by the measurement signals of a WF sensor - as described in the introduction above - would allow to compensate the actual WF distortion and to maintain the full data rate⁹.

Summary

WF sensors are nowadays integrated parts of many optical systems as on-line control elements of the emitted or received optical information. Which variant is selected, depends on the task: for robust industrial purposes the use of the Shack-Hartmann version is meanwhile standard, while for special work in science as astronomy or in technology as space applications modifications as the Hadamard types with higher resolution and much higher measurement speed are interesting. In the next issue of the *SPG Mitteilungen* we describe how to apply WF sensors to test large space telescopes.

⁹ See *SPG Mitteilungen* Nr. 50, p. 57 - 59 (2016)